

Numerical Channel-Floodplain Routing Model (CFRMod) Documentation– as used in Pizzuto & Huffman (2024)

1. Introduction to CFRMod

The numerical sediment routing model (CFRMod) simulates an idealized channel-floodplain system, where sediment moves through a stream channel during overbank flow, depositing sediment onto the floodplain and, conversely, eroding it back into the channel. The model is written in MATLAB code and was run on MATLAB R2024a. The model tests how floodplain storage and remobilization influence the downstream transport of an initial volume of sediment introduced at the upstream end of the channel. Sediment is routed through a series of reaches, cycling in and out of floodplain storage. Initially, no sediment exists in the system except for the introduced volume, and the model tracks its transport downstream as it moves between the channel and floodplains. The model runs for a specified number of timesteps, with no new sediment added after the initial input, allowing us to better understand the initial pulse's movement.

This document details the fundamental equations, numerical methods, model structure and associated variables, array grid manipulations, and model outputs and visualizations. A separate quick-start guide (entitled CFRMod_QuickStart) provides instructions for running the CFRMod MATLAB script and its associated storage regridding function.

2. Key Equations

The fundamental equations used in this model specify the spatial rate of change in non-dimensional concentration in the channel \tilde{C}_s and the time rate of change in non-dimensional floodplain storage \tilde{S}_t . Two versions of these equations can be used, one which specifies non-dimensional erosion \tilde{E} as a function of non-dimensional age \tilde{A} (Equations 1 and 2), A , and another which specifies \tilde{E} as independent of age (Equations 3 and 4).

Age-dependent form:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{C}_s}{\partial \tilde{x}} = \sum_{\tilde{A}} \tilde{E}(\tilde{A}) - \tilde{C}_s \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{S}_t}{\partial \tilde{t}} = \tilde{C}_s - \sum_{\tilde{A}} \tilde{E}(\tilde{A}) \quad (2)$$

Age-independent form:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{C}_s}{\partial \tilde{x}} = \tilde{S}_t - \tilde{C}_s \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{S}_t}{\partial \tilde{t}} = \tilde{C}_s - \tilde{S}_t \quad (4)$$

Additional equations are needed to define the dimensionless deposition \tilde{D} and \tilde{E} : (Equations 5 and 6-9):

$$\tilde{D} = \tilde{C}_s(\partial\tilde{t}) \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{E}(\tilde{A}) = \tilde{S}(\tilde{A})\tilde{f}_{w\tilde{A}}(\tilde{A}) \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{f}_{w\tilde{A}}(\tilde{A}) = 1 - \tilde{l}_s(\tilde{A}) + \tilde{l}_s(\tilde{A})\tilde{P}(\tilde{A}) \quad (7)$$

$$\tilde{l}_s(\tilde{A}) = \frac{1}{1 - e^{\tilde{k}(\tilde{A}_s - \tilde{A})}} \quad (8)$$

$$\tilde{P}(\tilde{A}) = \left(\frac{\tilde{P}_0 + \tilde{A}}{\tilde{P}_0} \right)^{-e} \quad (9)$$

These equations are derived in the supplemental material for Pizzuto & Huffman (2024).

3. Numerical Methods

The key equations listed above are solved numerically for application in the CFRMod.

3.1 Numerical Mesh

The equations are solved on a rectangular mesh of grid points aligned parallel to the \tilde{x} and \tilde{t} axes. Locations in the \tilde{x} -direction are indexed with the variable i , while locations in \tilde{t} are indexed with the variable j (Figure 1). The grid is staggered in space, with concentration values specified at integer values of i and storage values specified midway between concentration nodes (Figure 1). The grid is not staggered in time (i.e., both concentration and storage nodes are defined at integer values of j).

Figure 1. The numerical mesh for solving the concentration and storage equations. At any time step j and location i , concentration is known at node i, j , and the storage is known at $i+1/2$, either by initial and boundary conditions or from computations at a previous time step. The computations first determine the unknown concentration $\tilde{C}_{S_{i+1}}^j$ and subsequently, the unknown storage $\tilde{S}_{S_{i+1/2}}^{j+1}$ (though in practice the entire row of unknowns $\tilde{C}_{S_{i+1}}^j$ is first determined before solving for the row of unknown storage values $\tilde{S}_{S_{i+1/2}}^{j+1}$).

3.2 Initial and Boundary Conditions

Initial conditions specify sediment present in the spatial domain \tilde{x} at $\tilde{t} = 0$ (i.e., for $j = 1$). For problems of interest here, $\tilde{S}_{s_{i+1/2}}^1$ is set to 0 (i.e., no sediment stored on floodplains at $\tilde{t}=0$). To begin computations, a unit of sediment mass is placed at the origin, while no other sediment is present in the channel. These initial conditions are specified by setting $\tilde{C}_{s_1}^1 = 1/\partial\tilde{x}$ and $\tilde{C}_{s_i}^i = 0$ and for all nodes with $i > 1$.

Boundary conditions are also needed for $\tilde{t} > 0$. These are specified by setting $\tilde{C}_{s_1}^j = 0$ for all $j > 1$, consistent with the model grid structure of Figure 1, which requires that $\tilde{C}_{s_1}^j$ be specified in order to solve for $\tilde{C}_{s_2}^j$.

3.3 Numerical Approximation to Channelized Sediment Concentration

Recall the equation for channelized sediment concentration \tilde{C}_s (Equation 1). Here the storage term $\sum_{\tilde{A}} \tilde{E}(\tilde{A})$ is treated as a constant between grid points, making Equation 1 a first-order ordinary differential equation with constant coefficients that can be solved analytically given the known value $\tilde{C}_{s_i}^j$ as a boundary condition (Rabenstein, 1975), resulting in:

$$\tilde{C}_{s_{i+1}}^j = \sum_{\tilde{A}} \tilde{E}_{i+1/2}^j(\tilde{A}) + \left(\tilde{C}_{s_i}^j - \sum_{\tilde{A}} \tilde{E}_{i+1/2}^j(\tilde{A}) \right) e^{-\partial\tilde{x}} \quad (10)$$

where the summation term represents the dimensionless erosion rate of sediment stored at the storage grid point $(i+1/2, j)$, with the erosion rate weighted according to the dimensionless age, \tilde{A} , of the stored sediment (using Equations 6-9). For solving Equation (3) (i.e., erosion independent of the age of stored sediment), the summation term in (10) is replaced by the variable \tilde{S}_t .

To solve the storage equation (either Equation (2) or Equation (4)), concentrations need to be specified at the storage grid points between (i,j) and $(i+1,j)$. This is obtained by simple averaging:

$$\tilde{C}_{s_{i+1/2}}^j = \frac{\tilde{C}_{s_i}^j + \tilde{C}_{s_{i+1}}^j}{2} \quad (11)$$

For efficiency, the entire row along the x axis of concentrations $\tilde{C}_{s_{i+1}}^j$ is computed first using Equation (10). Then, the storage at time $j+1$, $\tilde{S}_{s_{i+1/2}}^{j+1}$, is computed along the entire \tilde{x} axis (the storage equations are discretized for the grid of Figure 1 below), after which the concentration values are computed at time $j+1$, $\tilde{C}_{s_{i+1}}^{j+1}$ (i.e., using equation (10) again..

3.4 Numerical Approximation the Storage Equation

The floodplain storage at time $j+1$ is calculated using the erosion from each age category (summation of $\tilde{E}(\tilde{A})$ from Equation 6) and deposition (Equation 5) values, such that the storage at time $j+1$ is:

$$\tilde{S}_{i+1/2}^{j+1} = \tilde{C}_{s_{i+1/2}}^j \partial\tilde{t} - \sum_{\tilde{A}} \tilde{E}_{i+1/2}^j(\tilde{A}) \partial\tilde{t} + \tilde{S}_{i+1/2}^j \quad (12)$$

3. Model Structure

The following details the spatial and temporal grid used, array architecture, and model structure. Note that all model variables are given in non-dimensional form unless otherwise stated. Variables are referred to as names given in the CFRMod script and are defined in Section 6.

3.1 Spatial and Temporal Grid

The spatial grid represents a length of stream channel and its adjacent floodplain. The total length of stream channel is divided into a series of reaches by a predetermined spatial step, dx_DL (denoted as $\partial\tilde{x}$ above). Note that dx_DL must be a small value to prevent numerical instability; Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) use a value of 0.0001. The boundaries between adjacent reaches are referred to here as "spatial nodes," each having a designated position i with $i=1$ representing the upstream-most node. Floodplain storage reservoirs are placed halfway between adjacent spatial nodes. The spatial grid is established in lines 20-23 of CFRMod.

The temporal grid represents the number of timesteps, dt_DL , needed to reach a maximum model run time, $tmax$ (dt_DL is equivalent to $\partial\tilde{t}$ used above). Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) use the value of 0.0001 for dt_DL (small enough to prevent numerical instability) and values of 0.1, 2, and 5 for $tmax$. The temporal grid is established in lines 25-29 of CFRMod.

3.2 Model Structure and Operation

Before the model starts, all needed variables and arrays are established (lines 18-58 of CFRMod). This includes the spatial and temporal grid defined above, the in-channel concentration arrays, the storage arrays, the time boundary arrays, and the erosion and deposition constants and arrays.

The model begins by establishing a time loop (Line 61) that iterates the model the desired number of times (as defined by the user in Lines 25-29). A conditional statement is then given in lines 62-72. Here, it is determined whether or not the model is at the first iteration; if so, no sediment is present in storage.

Once the calculation is done for all spatial steps at a given time step j , the model determines the volume of sediment deposited into storage at the current timestep (Dep_DL , Line 74, equivalent to the summation term in Equation (12)) for all locations between spatial nodes (i.e., where floodplain storage nodes are located). The deposited volume is then added to the storage array in the last row of the array (each row representing a given age category).

Lines 76-78 update the age boundaries of the storage array and the age categories of the storage array. The age boundaries represent the age of the contacts between storage sediment (Old_Tbound or New_Tbound). The newly deposited sediment in storage is given an upper age boundary of zero, while all previously stored age boundaries increase in age by the timestep (dt_DL). The age categories represent the average age between age boundaries (Old_Tbar) and are used to define a given row in the storage array and determine the amount of sediment erosion.

The weighting function ($\tilde{f}_{w\tilde{A}}(\tilde{A})$) of Equation (6) is defined for each age category (Lines 79-81) and is then used to determine the amount of sediment eroded from each age category. The

eroded volume from each age category is removed from the storage array (Line 84), and the storage array is converted back into a storage rate (Line 85) and then summed so it can be used when calculating the concentration during the next iteration (Line 86).

Finally, statements are added to reset the model for the next iteration. These include setting the concentration at the upstream-most spatial node equal to zero after the initial iteration (line 88), adding a new blank row to the storage array into which sediment will be deposited during the next iteration (Line 136), and resetting the weighting function and erosion arrays to be the same size as updated storage array (Lines 137-138). The model setup has returned to its initial form and can begin the next iteration.

4. Regridding Stored Sediment Volumes and Age Arrays

The model is set up to increase the array size temporally by one every iteration (representing a new “layer” of sediment being deposited). However, this approach fills the maximum array size allowed by MATLAB at longer model run times and drastically slows model efficiency. To combat this issue, an adaptive regridding function (`create_non_uniform_storage_grid.m`) is used to limit the maximum size of storage and age arrays while maintaining sufficient detail in model output data.

The adaptive grid generation is based on the following equation:

$$\text{New local grid spacing} = \text{old local grid spacing} * \text{constant} / (\text{local weighting function value})$$

where the "constant" is chosen so the first and last grid points and their y values remain unchanged after grid generation. The weighting function at grid point "i," $w(i)$, is (Eiseman, 1987):

$$w(i) = a + b * \text{abs}(y(i)) + c * (\text{abs}(\text{slope of } y \text{ versus } x \text{ at } i)) + d * (\text{abs}(\text{curvature of } y \text{ versus } x \text{ at } i))$$

where the “y” variable is the storage value at a given dimensionless age, “abs” is the absolute value function, and the values of a, b, c, and d are user-supplied constants (here, values of 0.1, 10, 0, and 0). Note that a large “a” value relative to other parameters results in a uniform grid, and the value “b” represents the weighting by the function value, which will be most useful in creating a sparse grid where storage values are small and a more detailed grid where storage values are large. Each of the “y” related values (y, slope, curvature) is scaled by its range [for example, for y itself, $(y - y_{\min}) / (y_{\max} - y_{\min})$], so the weighting is based on the range of the “y” related values rather than their actual numerical values.

The regridding function outputs include new storage (`New_Stored_DL`) and age boundary (`New_Tbound`) arrays that replace the “Old” equivalents of the same names. This function is implemented in lines 98-109 and only runs after a specified number of iterations (`regridtime`) has occurred rather than during each individual iteration.

5. Model Outputs and Visualization

Primary model outputs used by Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) include the amount of sediment stored in each age category between every spatial node (`Old_Stored_DL`), the age boundaries between each stored “layer” (`Old_Tbound`), the concentration of sediment in the channel at each spatial node (`Cs_DL`), as well as the spatial grid (x). The model is set up to save these variables at predetermined timesteps, here at times 0.1, 2, and 5. Additionally, the concentration in the channel is plotted as a function of distance at these three times.

6. List of Variable Names in the CFRMod MATLAB code

As_DL - Non-dimensional constant related to sediment age.

Cs_DL - a 1-by-numx array of zeros representing sediment concentration at each spatial node.

Cs_DL(1, 1) - Initial concentration value assigned to the first spatial node ($x=0$).

Cs_DL_bar - 1-by-(numx-1) array representing average concentration between adjacent spatial nodes.

Dep_DL - Array for newly deposited sediment for locations between spatial nodes.

dt_DL - Non-dimensional temporal step; should be a small value to avoid numerical instability.

dx_DL - Non-dimensional spatial step; should be a small value to avoid numerical instability.

Ew - Array that holds the amount of sediment eroded from storage by age category.

fwA - Array for the weighting function calculation for each age category.

i - Loop variable for indexing spatial nodes.

k_DL - Non-dimensional erosion constant.

Ls - Logistic switch value for each age category of stored sediment.

New_Stored_DL - The new storage array is to be filled out after regridding.

New_Tbound - The new time boundary array to be filled out after regridding.

numt - The total number of time steps the model will run is calculated as tmax divided by dt_DL and rounded.

numx - Total number of spatial nodes (length of x).

Old_Stored_DL - Non-dimensional storage array for every location between adjacent spatial nodes.

Old_Stored_DL_rate - Storage array in rate form for concentration calculations.

Old_Tbar - Array for the average age between time boundaries of stored sediment.

Old_Tbound - Array for the time boundaries of each storage array.

P - Power function value for each age category.

Po_DL - Non-dimensional constant derived from sediment characteristics.

power_law_exponent - Exponent value used in sediment transport calculations.

regridnum - Number each array to be regridded down to each time regridtime is reached.

regridtime - Number of timesteps that pass before files are regridded.

Stored_Sum_rate - Array of summed storage rates between adjacent storage nodes at every location.

t - Current timestep in the loop.

*t*_{max} - Maximum non-dimensional time the model will reach.

x - Non-dimensional spatial domain ranging from 0 (upstream) to 20 (downstream).

References

Eiseman, P.R. (1987). Adaptive Grid Generation. *Computer Methods in Applied Mathematics and Engineering*. 64:321-376.

Pizzuto, J., & Huffman, M.E., (2024). Compact models quantify the impact of floodplain storage on sediment delivery timescales and restoration efficiency. *Water Resources Research (Submitted)*.

Rabenstein, A.L. (1975). Elementary Differential Equations with Linear Algebra, 2nd Edition. Academic Press, 374 pp, Cambridge, MA, USA.